

A comprehensive methodology for criticality assessment of microvias in printed circuit board assemblies

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Abstract

The pursuit of smaller, lighter, and more efficient electronic devices in the electronics industry necessitates advanced packaging solutions. This study investigates the nuanced aspects of microvia technologies. Focusing on the impact of geometrical design parameters on the thermomechanical performance of microvias, Finite Element Method (FEM) simulations provide insights for various combinations of the geometrical variations.

The research underscores the critical role of lower microvia wall angles experience failures, corroborating literature predictions. Stress distribution analyses in global and submodel configurations offer consistent trends, emphasizing the importance of meticulous microvia design considerations. The observed strain values and localized failure regions further highlight the need for precision in design to mitigate vulnerabilities. This study contributes essential knowledge to ongoing efforts in advancing microelectronic reliability, sustainability, and innovation, setting the stage for further scientific increment in microelectronic industry.

Keywords: Via, Microvia, Printed Circuit Board Assembly (PCBA), Criticality Assessment, Reliability, Finite Element Analysis (FEA), Microelectronics.

1. Background

The electronics industry consistently requires packaging solutions that are smaller, lighter, faster, reliable, and cost-effective because of advancements in portable computers and wireless communications. Microvia technologies are essential for the advancement of cost-effective and highly compact printed circuit boards (PCBs). Microvias in substrates are specifically manufactured to suit the high input/output density of fine-pitch area-array packages, such as flip chips and chip scale packages (CSPs). Microvias demonstrate favourable electrical characteristics and minimal reflections in circuits with multiple layers [1]. The properties of microvia technology make it a practical choice for meeting the high-density demands of the industry.

The microelectronic reliability initiative, conducted by the “Microelectronics RELiability Driven by Artificial Intelligence (MIRELAI)” project in cooperation with the Polymer Competence Center Leoben (PCCL), Austria and Austria Technologie & Systemtechnik (AT&S) Leoben, Austria, seeks to address the challenges of reliability, sustainability, and verification in the production of microelectronic components. Additionally, the MIRELAI project aims to enhance Europe's innovation capacity and competitiveness in the market. The durability of microvia structures is crucial since they serve as essential interconnects between different layers. PCCL and AT&S are now conducting thorough simulations and experimental programs to build and analyse the reliability of microvia structures. This study aimed to investigate the impact of geometrical design parameters of microvias and their thermomechanical reliability. The findings obtained from FEM simulations will be utilised to optimise future designs in terms reliability.

2. Introduction

The increasing preference for miniaturisation and the need to manufacture micro scale components require the development of new tools, procedures, and a deeper understanding of how materials behave at such small scales.

Precision microvia drilling technology is crucial in contemporary high-density electronic packaging for the realization of compact devices and high-speed connectivity. PCBs and IC substrates typically are built of insulative polymer composite layers and thin structured copper sheets representing the active layers. The active layers are interconnected to each other by microvias, which are laser drilled and copper filled vias through the polymer composite layers [2].

Microvias are either blind or buried and have a diameter of 60-100 μm or less. Blind vias connect and out layer to one or more inner layers while buried vias connect two or more inner layers without any connection to the outer layers. The target pad for these microvias is around 150 μm [3,4]. Advanced laser drilling machines are able to achieve alignment precision of less than 10 μm [5].

Microvias can either be stacked or staggered when they are supposed to connect more than two layers. Stacked vias are directly atop of each other while staggered vias have a position offset between the layers. Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of a multilayer PCB featuring stacked and staggered microvias. A major difference is that the stacked vias have always to be filled while staggered vias can remain hollow.

Figure 1 A schematic representation of a multilayer PCB featuring stacked and staggered microvias.

Previous research [4,6–11] has primarily investigated the reliability of single-level unfilled microvias. These studies have identified various types of microvia failures, such as interfacial separation (separation between the base of the microvia and the target pad), barrel cracks, corner/knee cracks, and target pad cracks (also known as microvia pull out). These failures occur due to the thermomechanical stresses induced by a mismatch in the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between the metallisation layer in a microvia structure and the surrounding dielectric materials in the direction of the board thickness.

Additionally, scientists have created numerical models utilising the FEM to determine the specific stress and strain levels within a microvia structure. They have also utilised analytical models to predict the fatigue life of the microvias [7,8,12]. Prabhu et al. [12] and Ogunjimiet et al. [13] performed finite element analysis (FEA) on polymer-overlaid HDI microvia structures in multichip modules (MCMs) using 2D as well as 3D models. In their study, Prabhu et al. [12] examined the impact of accelerated temperature cycling and thermal shock on a microvia structure. They estimated the fatigue life of a structure by utilising the total strain range obtained from FEA. On the other hand, Ogunjimi et al. [13] discovered that the strain concentration factor, copper ductility, and microvia wall thickness had more pronounced influences on microvia reliability than the wall angle and dielectric layer thickness.

Researchers [7,8,14] have examined the impact of geometry and material characteristics on the reliability of microvias using FEA.

They discovered that variations in microvia wall thickness, wall angle, diameter, dielectric thickness, or dielectric quality lead to distinct amounts of stress and strain. Wang and Lai [14] utilised the submodelling technique in FEA to examine the possible locations of failure in the microvias. According to their model, filled microvias exhibit reduced stress levels compared to non-filled microvias.

It can be concluded, that the basis for the evaluation of the microvia performance is the detailed knowledge of the local stress situation. The local stress situation again depends on the global PCB build-up, manufacturing influences, environmental conditions and loading conditions. Extensive research has been performed in the past to precisely describe the local stress situation using multi-physics simulation approaches considering all relevant influence factors. Especially the scale mismatch between global PCB size (several centimetres) and critical local failures (micrometeor range) is a demanding challenge. Approaches, as material homogenization or submodeling have been successfully used in literature for the localized study of PCBs and have the potential to be applied to analyse microvias [15–31].

The authors of this work conducted a comparison of global model (board level) and submodel (single microvia chosen from the global model) simulation results to accurately anticipate the stress evolution caused by the PCB reflow process and determine the thermomechanical effect on these structures. A scripted approach automatically studying the effect of

via design parameters is introduced. The work is a prestudy to generate comprehensive data for a machine learning approach, paving the way for advanced analysis and optimization strategies in future microvia designs.

3. Modelling and simulation

The modelling of the microvias in this work has been performed using the commercial finite element software Abaqus 2022, Dassault Systèmes, Vélizy-Villacoublaym, France. The scripting to automatize the simulation model generation has been performed using Python v2.7.18.

The presented approach is based on a ‘submodeling’ technique, which makes use of a global and local model analysis. The deformation results from the global model under defined loading conditions are transferred via interface boundary conditions to a model of a local area of interest. The advantage of the approach is that the local model can have a refined mesh and more complex material models. Thus, the computational effort can be kept at an acceptable level, while getting detailed local results.

The global model in this study is a simplified three-four-layer PCB (see Figure 2) featuring microvias. In future work it can be substituted by any complex PCB build up. The objective is to consider influences of the global board design on the local behaviour.

Figure 2 Microvias organised in a PCB with equal spacing between each other (global model, 6000 X 6000 μm).

The local model in this work is a cut-out of a single microvia from the global model (compare Figure 3). The loading conditions for both, the global and local model were defined as a thermal load ranging from 20 °C to 260 °C, resembling the reflow process. The models were meshed using hexahedral elements, namely the C3D8R, which are 8-node linear brick elements with reduced integration and hourglass control. The global model mesh size was 0.5 mm compared to 0.009 mm.

Figure 3 Stack-up of the copper (thin layer), dielectric material (thick layer) and microvia in the center.

The dimensions of the copper and dielectric layers used in the local FE model are given in Table 1.

The material data and calibrated material models applied for the individual materials are based on foregoing research and results [16]. The considered material model for both copper and dielectric is a temperature dependent isotropic linear elastic model. A simplified material behaviour has been assumed and no anisotropy, viscoelasticity, plasticity or damage parameter was considered for the time being, as the focus of the presented work was on the method development only.

However, the simplifications have to be considered while interpreting the results. Based on the used linear elastic material model, the results will not give realistic stress and strain values, but will only allow for a trend analysis, which again is sufficient to evaluate the proposed approach.

Table 1 Dimensions of copper and prepreg layers in the local FE model.

Material	Dimensions (L x W x H) (μm)
Copper layer	600 x 600 x 15
Dielectric layer (prepreg)	600 x 600 x 65

Python scripting was used to automate the FE model generation for both, the global and local model. Thus, a range of different parameters of the via geometry could be analysed (compare Figure 4). Global and local FE-models were generated for all combinations of the listed parameters for microvia angle and microvia radius (bottom) in Table 2.

Figure 4 Schematic representation of the analysed microvia design parameters

Table 2 Different microvia parameters considered for the studies.

Parameters	Variations
Microvia angle ($^{\circ}$)	90, 100, 110, 120, 130, 140, 150
Radius (μm)	40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 65, 70, 75, 80
Height (μm)	65

Being aware that realistic microvia angles only range to 130° extreme angles have been studied to see the theoretical potential. Further, the automatised evaluation of the local Mises stress and principal strain situation was done within the Python script. The resulting Mises stress and principal strain values of the ring of elements around the upper diameter of the copper via (compare Figure 7) was averaged.

4. Result and discussion

The local stress situation in the microvias result from the CTE mismatch between the dielectric material and copper and is affected by the microvia's shape and size. At 260°C , the CTE mismatch peaks, resulting in the highest thermomechanical stress levels in the microvias.

When interpreting the local stress situation two major effects have to be considered: 1) a linear elastic material model has been used for which reason the local stresses within the copper will be higher than the copper yield stress. 2) The mesh size of the global and the local model is not suited to obtain valid absolute stress values for now. The corner between

the via and pad would require modelling of the very small radius and a mesh size below 0.1 μm in order to obtain realistic stress values. For now, a sharp edge is considered with a mesh size of 9 μm for the local model and a mesh size of 30 to 500 μm in the global model. The local model will thus give much higher stresses for local stress concentrations, but will still not give a realistic absolute value.

The focus of the work was to maximise the computational efficiency to be able to screen a large range of parameters, while still being able to get reliable trends. Thus, the presented work can be the basis for ongoing research introducing a refined damage model and criticality assessment performed potentially on a further localized model.

The simulation times for the current simulation models were about 10 minutes for the global model (25600 elements) and 30 minutes for the local model (131776 to 139500 elements) with submodel boundary conditions on an Intel Xenon Silver 4216 CPU @2.10 GHz (15 cores, 32 threads) workstation.

The resulting trends for stress and strain of the global and local models are given in Figures 5 and Figure 6 and Figure 8 and 9 respectively. The presented results for Mises stress and principal strain represent the averaged values of the elements of the upper copper pad along and closest to the corner between upper copper pad and via (compare Figure 7).

For the global model the trends show that the Mises stress and principal strain is increasing with the via radius and decreasing with the via angle. A reduced stress due to the increased angle is expected as the stress concentration is higher for smaller angles. The influence on the radius can be attributed to the increased out of plane strength of thicker vias introducing a larger out of plane thermal expansion mismatch between via and dielectric material.

Figure 5 Mises stress distribution in global model over microvia radius at different microvia angles.

Figure 6 Maximum principal strain distribution in global model

For the local models the evaluated stress and strain situation changes significantly. The stress distribution with the stress maximum at the corner between via and copper pad is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Cross-section of a microvia submodel with 80um radius and 100° angle. The red marking shows the stress peak and indicates the evaluation region.

The trends for the Mises stress for the local model (see Figure 8) are comparable to the global model even when the total values are significantly higher. That can be explained by the discussed mesh size effect. Further, at smaller angles the difference between the models is less pronounced. The principal strain shows again the same trend for the via angles, but the influence of the radius is vice versa. Higher microvia radii decrease the maximum principal strain. That indicates that the stress tensor is affected by the changing radius and that with lower radii the stress is more directed. As a consequence, according to the local model results higher vias with increased radii are more prone to yielding but less prone to initiate a crack. That is an important effect which is not evident in the global model and could lead to misinterpretation of parameter effects.

Figure 8 Mises stress distribution in submodel over microvia radius at different microvia angles.

Figure 9 Maximum principal strain distribution in submodel.

The trends for higher strain values at lower microvia angles have been confirmed in literature [32], while radius effects have not been published yet to the knowledge of the authors.

The pursuit of non-mesh size dependent results and a reliable damage assessment poses a significant challenge, particularly when constrained by feasible mesh sizes for parameter studies.

5. Conclusion and outlook

In this study, the criticality assessment of microvias in PCBAs was examined through a combination of FEM simulations and analysis of geometrical design parameters. The investigation underscores the impact of design variations on the local microvia stress situation under thermomechanical loads within the PCBAs.

From the FEM simulations, it was demonstrated that microvias with lower wall angles are more vulnerable to failure under thermal loading conditions, consistent with previous literature predictions. Moreover, the study revealed that variations in microvia radii influence stress levels and stress orientations.

Recognizing the identified limitations, the study outlined strategic directions for future research. An approach for a mesh independent criticality assessment based on a refined mesh and advanced material models will be worked on. At the same time, the aim is to keep the model computationally efficient so that it is suitable for extended parameter studies. The generated data is planned to be the basis for the training of surrogate models. These surrogate models again are planned to enable a full field analysis of all individual vias within a PCBA.

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